

USE OF UZBEK FOLKLORE IN EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES TO EDUCATE STUDENTS IN THE SPIRIT OF PATRIOTISM

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Abstract: *Nowadays development of any country is owing to the implementation of the initiatives on development of the education, improvement of the quality of the education, improving the role and place of the teachers in the society and appreciating their deeds.*

Studying folklore, which reflect understanding and showing individuality of a nation, motivations, life style and outlook, is to study history of ethnos, their customs, traditions, feelings, past, present and future. Popular epics play an important role in the spiritual perfection of the mankind. There has analyzed significance of the studying folklore in the educational system of Uzbekistan and educational, training, and developing aims of the lesson which dedicated to teach Uzbek and English folk epics on the basis of comparative-typological analysis were structured in this article.

Key words: *The folklore, the spiritual perfection, patriotism, a fairy tale.*

The folklore, created many centuries before the written literature, has been living on up to these days. The Uzbek folklore, which served as a great source in the formation of the written literature, includes many genres such as poems, legends, tales, songs, sayings and riddles, and they reflect the history, domestic culture, traditions and mentality of the nation. the history of poetic thought of the Oriental peoples is of common origin such as symbols, artistic style, ideas of glorification of human being, comprehension of human beings and the world, faithfulness, loyalty in its philosophical nature found in these epics share the same roots. Meanwhile divine support and recognition of positive creativity i.e. psychology of artistic creativity are reflected in them. By their nature the epic motives are in harmony with mythological and religious and traditional views. According to the “Education program for the secondary education” for the subject of literature approved in 1999 by the “State standards of the secondary education”, the content of the meaning of the subject of literature includes the studying the unique samples of folklore of Uzbek, fraternal and foreign nations, forming the skills of understanding and analyzing the read eposes, their comparative analysis

by comprehending the theoretical information, and development of the pupils' oral and written skills.

The younger generation is the foundation of our future. Thus we need to pay more attention to primary education. The main part of the important task of educating primary school students is carried out in reading classes. The textbooks also cover a wide range of folklore that students love to read. Folklore includes fairy tales, epics, legends, narrations, songs, folk songs, riddles, parables anecdotes and stories. Folklore has long been a source of education.

The physical and spiritual development and intellectual potential of the younger generation play an important role in the development of society, the destiny of the country and the nation. As the head of our state Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted, “Today, as the world is changing rapidly and various new threats and dangers that threaten the stability and sustainable development of peoples are emerging, it is more important than ever to focus on the spirituality and enlightenment, moral education, youth education and the pursuit of perfection.”

A number of important document improving the state youth policy identified in the Action Strategy for the five main initiatives of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, protection of the rights and interests of young people and on creating the necessary conditions for their harmonious development have been adopted, practical work has been done, certain results have been achieved. However, the work to be done in this area is always extensive and relevant. In this regard, under the leadership of the President, on March 19, 2019, in the video

conference "On the implementation of the 5 main initiatives in the effective organization of work with youth increasing interest to read a book, to culture, art, sports and information technology", issues related to youth development were discussed and 5 main initiatives in this area were put forward. These are followings:

The first initiative serves to increase the interest and highlight the talent of young people in music, painting, literature, theater and other arts.

These condinitiative is aimed at creating the necessary conditions for young people to be fit and show their abilities in sports.

The third initiative is aimed at promoting the effective use of computer technology and the Internet among the population and youth.

The fourth initiative is aimed at increasing the spirituality of young people and organizing the systematic work to promote reading among them.

The fifth initiative implies the issues regarding the employment of women. According to the fourth initiative, creating a love for books from an early age in young people, the formation of critical thinking and a broad outlook are a solid foundation in their lives.

The school is an educational institution, and the future of the individual depends on how it is implemented in the institution, and how the teacher, being an educator, reacts to his duties and responsibilities. This is the basis for educating a harmoniously developed person, first of all, as a selfless person for the society and for the people among he lives.

Oral literature created by the people is called folklore. Longman Advanced Learners' Dictionary defines "Folklore" is originally an English word; "Folk" is people, "Lore" is knowledge or information about a subject, for example nature or magic, that is not written down but is passed from person to person. Together they mean "folk wisdom". Uzbek folklore, consisting of various genres, is an art of expression that reflects the worldview, dreams and aspirations of the Uzbek people. Folklore includes fairy tales, epics, legends, narrations, songs, lapars, riddles, parables, anecdotes and stories.

A fairy tale is a folklore work. That is why fairy tales are a product of oral tradition and are told in many ways, spread by word of mouth. They are traditional, have unknown creator, and a plot is told in several variants among the people. The artistic form and poetics of fairy tales are unique. Fantastic fiction is associated with the realities of life and reflects the ancient concepts, customs and rituals themselves. One of the hallmarks of a fairy tale is that the events and happenings are interpreted by the narrator and the listener not as "real events" but as "unrealones". Therefore, in fairy tales, the place and time of events are described in an ambiguous general way. In addition, the role of fairy tales in terms of time and place varies. It is obvious that fairy tales differ from other genres of folklore in their peculiarities.

The use of fairy tales has a positive effect on both increasing readers' interest in knowledge and educating them to become perfect human beings.

Patriotism is a great virtue. The homeland is the place where a person is born, where his umbilical cord blood is shed, where he spends his childhood and youth, where he is educated, and where he always misses when he travels. Because of the sense of homeland, a person loves the house he lives in, the neighborhood he lives in, the city-village, the Motherland, makes it prosperous, glorifies and protects its honor. The family, as the backbone of

society, is a place where our children develop feelings of love for the country and the Motherland.

Patriotism is a high belief, a sense of responsibility to the motherland and the nation, a high duty. The saying, which is passed down from ancestors to generations, says, "Loving one's country is a matter of faith." If we look at our long history, we will see that the sense of patriotism has long been respected by our people. We can learn about the behavior of famous people who grew up among our ancestors, their hard work for the development of the country, the works that have come down to us, as well as the folklore. Al-Khwarizmi, Abu Ali ibn Sino, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Umar Khayyam, Yusuf Khas Hajib, At-Termizi, Ahmad Yassavi, Imam Bukhari, Bahauddin Naqshband, Amir Temur, Mirzo Ulugbek, Alisher Navoi, Babur, Uvaysi, Nodirabegim, The life and creative activity of Abdulla Avloni, Abdurauf Fitrat, Anbar Otin, Behbudi, Cholpon, especially the ideas of faith in the motherland are extremely important for the development of our new society.

First of all, students should be interested in the national and cultural heritage, language, traditions and customs of their people, as well as in the spiritual riches of other nations. Special attention should be paid to expanding the scope of his knowledge, acquaintance with the culture of different peoples. From national values: the nature of the motherland, national folk art, national aesthetic sources of traditions, artistic culture, history of the East, including Uzbekistan, in the formation of the spirit of national moral traditions in students, national self expression, internationalism and should be used in the development of patriotic feelings. Spiritual values and ideas unite students of different nationalities and help to organize educational and labor activities. If we look at the past, the rich experience of folk pedagogy in the upbringing of children has not been fully implemented, the pedagogical views of great scholars, oriental traditions, rich traditions, the lack of implementation has led to many shortcomings in education. After the independence of Uzbekistan, the implementation of major reforms in the social, economic, cultural and spiritual spheres of society has set important tasks for the education of future generations.

First of all, it requires the next generation to have a high level of knowledge, a broad outlook and faith that can confidently adapt to these changes. In order to educate the younger generation in the spirit of patriotism, to inculcate the concepts of national consciousness, national pride, they must be spiritually healthy. Spiritual health, on the other hand, is closely linked to physical and mental health.

Patriotism is a sense of pride in one's homeland, its history and achievements. The desire to make our country more beautiful, rich and happy. It is courage, diligence and the strength of the people. It is an attitude to the vast territories of the country, its natural resources, its heroic historical past and today's conflicting realities, the people living in it, their national dignity, culture , custom. So when we study patriotism, it includes the following:

-A sense of love for your family and the places where a person was born and raised;

- Respect for the people of their village, city, their people, language and culture;

-The desire to care for other people and the interests of the homeland;-
To understand the people around them, their place of residence, their duties to the Motherland, to protect their honor and dignity, freedom and independence, to be ready to defend the Motherland;

- Responsibility for the fate of the Motherland and its people, their future, expressed in the desire to dedicate themselves to their work, to increase the power and prosperity of the Motherland;

- Humanity, compassion, universal values.

Using Uzbek folklore is very effective way of improving the feeling of patriotism.

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